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WP4 (Taiwan) Civil Society Engagement Report

First Workshop on HRJust: COVID-19 Governance in Taiwan, October 26, 2024

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First Workshop: COVID-19 Governance in Taiwan, 26 October, 2024

The WP4 Taiwan team hosted 2 Workshops on COVID-19 Governance as part of our programme of Civil Society Engagement in the second year of HRJust, with the first one aimed at generating ideas and key points, and the second one bringing all participants back and sharing our preliminary research findings with them.

This report sets out key issues arising at the first Workshop, which took place on October 26, 2024, in Taipei,

Among the participants were workers from a number of relevant NGOs, members of the union for pilots, the Air Line Pilots Association (ALPA-T), medical staff from Taiwan's Center for Disease Control (CDC), Administrative Appeals Commission members, a Supreme Administrative Court judge, and law professors. Their experiences and expertise allowed us to reflect on our observations so far and gain a deeper understanding of COVID-19 governance in Taiwan, especially what issues the government had neglected.

Various topics were covered in this Workshop, including the process of governmental policy-making and internal evaluation, criticisms from civil society, and oversight by the checking power.

WP4's co-lead, Shun-Ling Chen opened the event with a brief introduction of HRJust and the Civil Society Engagement process. NGO workers from the Taiwan Association for Human Rights (TAHR, contributing on privacy and digital rights) and the Taiwan International Workers' Association (TIWA, contributing on migration) presented their experiences of advocacy of human rights and COVID-19 governance. For instance, TAHR reported how they had filed several FOIA requests regarding digital preventive measures, expressing concerns about "function creep" during the COVID-19 period. Measures such as "digital fencing" (using cell phone signals to triangulate the owner's location) were first introduced to ensure people quarantined at home, hotel, or centralized facility, but then extended to those who were under so-called "self-monitoring" requirements and thus were not allowed to cluster and attend social events.

TIWA shared how undocumented migrant workers were blamed as virus spreaders after they lost contact with employers, and they were afraid of being tracked by cellphone GPS because of their illegal status and the risk of being deported. In addition, migrant workers were restricted from buying essentials and going out, and tended to live in narrow, small spaces that could readily generate cluster infections. In parallel, they faced a severe lack of epidemic information

and resources, such as masks and products containing alcohol for infection control.

During the pandemic, the pilots' union organized their members to file lawsuits to challenge quarantine measures. As some cases are still pending in the Supreme Administrative Court, WP4 Taiwan arranged to have a separate meeting with the pilots' union prior to the Workshop and have WP4's Hui-Chieh Su present the experiences of pilots, especially the heavy burden of the quarantine policy imposed on them. Since air pilots frequently enter and exit the border due to their occupational characteristics, they were continuously quarantined and PCR tested. Even in the few days they were out of quarantine, their mobility was restricted under the "self-monitoring" requirements before they had to fly again. In Fall 2021, the government backtracked on a policy to exempt fully vaccinated pilots from quarantine. Due to that, pilots petitioned the court for relief under the Habeas Corpus Act. Most of these petitions were rejected by the court as the court refused to consider quarantine at home or in hotels as "imprisonment" or "detention". In the first two years, the administrative court generally declined to offer any substantive examination and found the administrative dispositions valid, treating their role in reviewing the cases as a formality. But in the end, a court decision turned the tide. (For detail, see below)

Members of the Administrative Appeals Commission in Taipei City and MOHW, along with an Administrative Supreme Court judge, shared their experiences of reviewing cases, including vaccination, quarantine, mask mandates, and Habeas Corpus cases, which also demonstrated the inadequacy of the procedures for announcing pandemic measures. Among these, there was a leading case that broke through the narrow interpretation of the scope of the Habeas Corpus Act. In January 2022, the Taipei High Administrative Court went beyond the previous approach of viewing the court's role in considering the applicability or not of the Habeas Corpus Act as a mere formality. In this case, which was also brought by a pilot, the court ruled that home quarantine did indeed fall under the category of "detention" as defined by the Habeas Corpus Act and examined the substantive legality of administrative dispositions for the first time.¹

However, the member of the Administrative Appeals Commission in Taipei City also expressed the difficulty of making a judgment when the pandemic was still developing. He noted that "it was not easy to challenge pandemic measures promptly due to the unpredictable nature of the crisis." Members of the Administrative Appeals Commission in MOHW further observed that "since the

¹ Taipei High Administrative Court Ruling, Appeal for Habeas Corpus Case, No. 1, 2022. (臺北高等行政法院111年行提抗字第1號裁定)

government always used the rhetoric of ‘right to life trumps everything’ as an apparent justification for sacrificing all other human rights, those measures are easily regarded as legitimate and accepted by the general public.”

Following that, the judge and the two Commission members shed light on how the regulations could be improved, drawing on their experiences of navigating the pandemic. All three believed that a comprehensive assessment of proportionality remains vital once the emergency has subsided

To address concerns raised by other participants, a CDC medical officer explained the decision-making mechanism and process of the Central Epidemic Command Center (CECC), including the organization and division between CECC and the CDC/the Ministry of Health and Welfare (MOHW). The medical officer also noted that several objections based on legal and ethical concerns were raised during CECC’s meetings. For instance, the restrictions on nationals returning to Taiwan and the annotation of potential contact history on NHI cards during specific outbreaks were criticized for overly restricting individuals’ right to return to their own countries and privacy. However, some of these internal critiques were not addressed and remained invisible to the public once the measures took effect.

Lastly, law professors focused on whether issuing an emergency decree was necessary when facing the COVID-19 pandemic. Neither saw the need to declare emergency status during the pandemic in Taiwan, and both criticized the legislation for giving the administration too much discretion during COVID. One professor considered that the normal legal system was capable of responding to the emergency caused by COVID-19 in Taiwan. The main problem was that, while congressional sessions were uninterrupted, the legislation did not keep up with the changes in the pandemic. Another professor argued that, even though the government did not issue an emergency decree, it failed to comply with the rule of law and democracy when taking several pandemic preventive measures. Hence, the reality is not far from an emergency status, even though none was officially declared.

During Q&A, participants mostly focused on the working of the CECC, as much of it remained unclear to the public, This lack of transparency and understanding suggests that it may be difficult to hold the organisation to account.